

Phytochemical diversity of essential oils from wild *Salvia verticillata* L. populations across different regions of Bulgaria

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Abstract

Salvia is the largest genus within the Lamiaceae family, comprising more than 900 species, many of which have long-standing ethnobotanical relevance and well-documented traditional usage in folk medicine across Europe, Asia, and the Mediterranean region. *Salvia verticillata* L. is a comparatively underexplored species, characterized by pronounced phytochemical richness and promising pharmacological potential. The present study aimed to investigate the phytochemical diversity and chemical variability of essential oils obtained from wild *S. verticillata* populations collected from three distinct regions of Bulgaria. Gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (GC–MS) was employed for essential oil characterization, and descriptive statistical analysis was performed. Comparative analysis revealed moderate geographical variation in the relative abundance of the major constituents— β -caryophyllene, humulene, and bicyclogermacrene—whereas germacrene D exhibited pronounced regional variability. Additionally, several minor constituents showed location-dependent presence or absence. These findings demonstrate that geographical origin may influence the phytochemical diversity of *S. verticillata* essential oils.

Keywords

Chemogeographical variation, essential oils, GC–MS, Lamiaceae, *Salvia verticillata*, β -caryophyllene, traditional medicine

Introduction

The Lamiaceae family is regarded as one of the most widespread and diverse families in the kingdom Plantae, including more than 200 genera and over 3000 species (Ivanova et al. 2024). The family is associated with a great variety of aromatic plants, frequently used in the treatment of various diseases and conditions (Uritu et al. 2018). Some of the most important genera in the Lamiaceae family include *Salvia*, *Scutellaria*, *Stachys*, *Plectranthus*, *Hyptis*, *Vitex*, and *Thymus*, among others.

Salvia, or sage, is considered the largest genus in this family and includes more than 900 species, many of which have been used by humans since ancient times as medicinal plants (Sharifi-Rad et al. 2018). Due to the large number of active compounds in essential oils (EOs) and extracts, sage is associated with a long and well-documented ethnobotanical history, with numerous species traditionally used in folk medicine for the treatment of gastrointestinal, respiratory, cardiovascular, inflammatory, and infectious disorders across Europe, the Mediterranean, and Western Asia (Sirakov et al. 2005; Turiiski et al. 2006; Uritu et al. 2018). The great diversity of the genus, phytochemical abundance, and broad-spectrum pharmacological activities of *Salvia* species indicate the significant potential of the genus for discovering new biologically active compounds (Zhumaliyeva et al. 2023). Some of the most important and studied plants from the genus *Salvia* include *S. officinalis* (common sage), *S. lavandulifolia* (Spanish sage), *S. sclarea* (clary sage), *S. miltiorrhiza* (danshen), and *S. hispanica* (chia) (Sharifi-Rad et al. 2018).

Salvia verticillata L. (*S. verticillata* or lilac sage, Fig. 1) is an example of a less-explored *Salvia* species that could be a source of compounds with high therapeutic value. *S. verticillata* is a herbaceous perennial plant native to Central and Eastern Europe and Western Asia, where it grows under continental climatic conditions (Giuliani et al. 2018). The plant is characterized by erect and branched stems, reaching a height of 80 cm, and together with the leaves, they are covered with taeniate hairs. The simple, opposite, pointed, and serrated leaves can be heart-shaped or ovate-triangular, with prominent veins on the lower

Figure 1. Wild-growing *Salvia verticillata* L.

surface. The flowers are lilac or lilac-blue, bilobed, and bisexual; covered with papilliform short hairs; and clustered in axillary or terminal inflorescences. The tubular calyxes are covered with white or purple hairs, and the pedicels with antrorse hairs. The rhizome of the perennial plant *S. verticillata* is ascending or subhorizontal, brown, and up to 10 mm thick. The seeds are light brown, smooth, rounded, and ovoid. Lilac sage is a cross-pollinated plant that grows at an altitude of up to 1000 m and flowers in the second year from May to September (Giuliani et al. 2018; Bussmann et al. 2020).

The composition of *S. verticillata* EOs and extracts could vary considerably, depending on the geographical region; however, the main groups of secondary metabolites are phenolic compounds (phenolic acids and flavonoids) and terpenes (monoterpenes and diterpenes). The extracts mainly contain caffeic acid, rosmarinic acid, different types of salvianolic acids, and the flavonoid apigenin (Katanić Stanković et al. 2020; Ivanova et al. 2024). The EOs are characterized by the presence of volatile compounds, such as β -caryophyllene, germacrene D, α -humulene, muurolene, α - and β -pinene, β -phellandrene, 1,8-cineole, and spathulenol (Katanić Stanković et al. 2020; Ivanova et al. 2024).

S. verticillata is not usually a domesticated and locally adapted plant such as *S. officinalis*. However, it is used for its biological activities and in the treatment of various ailments and occupies an important place in regional ethnomedicine (Katanić Stanković et al. 2020). Ethnobotanical data from Eastern Europe report the use of its leaves and aerial parts primarily as infusions and decoctions for gastrointestinal complaints, including abdominal pain, constipation, nausea, and indigestion, as well as for colds, cough, and mild inflammatory conditions (Nicolescu et al. 2026). In some traditions, decoctions have also been employed in the management of endocrine conditions, while topical applications have been used for skin irritations and wound-related conditions (Kostić et al. 2022; Nicolescu et al. 2026). These traditional uses suggest a broad therapeutic potential for *S. verticillata* L., supporting contemporary interest in its phytochemical composition and biological activity (Kostić et al. 2022; Nicolescu et al. 2026).

The plant is associated with considerable therapeutic potential. However, further studies are required to substantiate its efficacy and safety, as well as to establish standardized protocols for the preparation and quality control of its EOs and extracts. *S. verticillata* L. has demonstrated pronounced antioxidant activity, along with anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, and antifungal properties (Ivanova et al. 2024). In addition, this species has been proposed as a promising candidate for wound-healing applications by supporting the re-epithelialization process (Gushiken et al. 2022). Lilac sage may also hold potential in the management of neurodegenerative disorders such as Alzheimer's disease, as it is a source of biologically active compounds exhibiting acetylcholinesterase inhibitor activity (Katanić Stanković et al. 2020).

The aim of the present study was to assess the phytochemical diversity and chemogeographical variation of EOs isolated from wild *S. verticillata* populations collected from three distinct regions of Bulgaria. To the best of current knowledge, this work represents the first investigation of the EO composition of *S. verticillata* populations originating from Bulgaria.

Materials and methods

Plant material

The aerial parts (stems, leaves, and flowers) of wild-growing *S. verticillata* L. were collected during the flowering period in June–July from three different locations in Bulgaria (Table 1). The plants were authenticated according to Stoyanov et al. (2021), and voucher specimens were deposited in the Herbarium of the Agricultural University of Plovdiv, Bulgaria. The plant materials were air-dried at room temperature prior to the isolation of the EOs.

Chemicals and reagents

The retention indices (RIs) were determined using the following hydrocarbons: nonane ($\geq 99\%$), decane ($\geq 99\%$), undecane ($\geq 99\%$), dodecane (99%), tridecane ($\geq 99\%$), tetradecane ($\geq 99\%$), and hexadecane ($\geq 99\%$), purchased from Merck KGaA (Darmstadt, Germany). For the dilution of the EO, hexane (Thermo Fisher Scientific GmbH, Bremen, Germany) was used.

Isolation of the essential oils

For the isolation of the EOs, the air-dried aerial parts of *S. verticillata* L. were hydrodistilled for 4 h using a Clevenger-type apparatus. The EOs were collected, dried over anhydrous sodium sulfate, and stored in dark glass vials at 4 °C prior to gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (GC–MS) analysis.

Chromatographic conditions

GC–MS was used to carry out the analysis of the EOs. The separation of the volatile compounds was achieved with a Bruker Scion 436-GC SQ MS (Bremen, Germany), equipped with a Zebron ZB-5MSplus capillary column (30 m \times 0.25 mm i.d. and 0.25 μ m film thickness). Helium was used as the carrier gas at a constant flow rate of 1 mL/min. The injection volume was 1 μ L. The injector temperature was set to 250 °C, with a split ratio of 1:30. The

oven temperature was set at 60 °C for 2 min, then increased to 110 °C at a rate of 10 °C/min. This was followed by raising the temperature to 180 °C at a rate of 5 °C/min, then increasing it to 280 °C at a rate of 15 °C/min, and holding it for 2 min. The detector temperature was set to 300 °C. The mass spectra were collected in full-scan mode with a mass range of 50–350 m/z (Ivanova et al. 2025). To identify the constituents of the EOs, their MS spectra and RIs were compared with spectral data from the Wiley NIST11 Mass Spectral Library (NIST11/2011/EPA/NIH) and literature data. The RI values of the separated compounds were determined based on the retention times of the C8–C20 *n*-alkane series, injected under the same conditions described above. The relative peak area percentages represent the mean of three independent measurements. The standard error of the mean was omitted, as it was not more than 2%.

Statistical analysis

Descriptive statistical analysis was performed using IBM SPSS Statistics 30. The relative abundances (%) of EO constituents identified by GC–MS were summarized using descriptive measures. Comparative visualization of the major constituents among *S. verticillata* populations from the three geographical regions was carried out using clustered bar charts. No inferential statistical analyses were applied, as the study focused on describing phytochemical diversity and geographical variation in EO composition.

Results and discussion

Volatile constituents of *Salvia verticillata* L. essential oils

The aerial parts of three wild *S. verticillata* populations were used to obtain EOs: Panagyurishte (SV1), Karlovo (SV2), and Batak (SV3). The EOs were pale yellow in color, with a characteristically intense herbal, woody, and pleasant aroma. The chemical composition of the EOs was determined by gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (GC–MS). A total of 47, 26, and 46 volatile components were identified in the EOs from wild-growing *S. verticillata* L., representing 95.88%, 94.58%, and 96.85% of the total oil content for SV1, SV2, and SV3, respectively. The analysis revealed differences in the number of volatile compounds identified in SV1 and SV3 EOs compared to SV2 EO. The chemical composition of the analyzed *S. verticillata* EOs is presented with retention indices, formulas, compound class, and percentage of the total EO in Table 2, and the chromatograms from the GC–MS analysis are presented in Fig. 2.

Table 1. Sample origin, coordinates, collection period, and voucher specimens of *S. verticillata* L.

Analysed sample origin	Coordinates	Collection period	Voucher number	Used abbreviation
Panagyurishte region	42°33'44"N, 24°11'46"E	June	063530	SV1
Karlovo region	42°38'51"N, 24°48'47"E	June	063531	SV2
Batak region	41°58'26"N, 24°12'42"E	July	063582	SV3

Table 2. Volatile constituents of wild *S. verticillata* EOs from different locations in Bulgaria, as a percentage of the total EO.

Nº	Compound	RI	Formula	Class of compound	SV1 (%)	SV2 (%)	SV3 (%)
1	α -Thujene	945	C ₁₀ H ₁₆	MH	0.11	-	0.23
2	α -Pinene	951	C ₁₀ H ₁₆	MH	0.39	1.10	0.59
3	Sabinene	983	C ₁₀ H ₁₆	MH	0.28	0.37	0.69
4	1-Octen-3-ol	986	C ₈ H ₁₆ O	O	0.09	-	0.12
5	β -Pinene	988	C ₁₀ H ₁₆	MH	0.12	0.50	0.35
6	β -Myrcene	994	C ₁₀ H ₁₆	MH	0.58	0.52	0.99
7	Pseudolimonene	1012	C ₁₀ H ₁₆	MH	0.12	-	0.17
8	α -Phellandrene	1015	C ₁₀ H ₁₆	MH	0.12	-	0.23
9	3-Carene	1018	C ₁₀ H ₁₆	MH	0.40	-	0.13
10	α -Terpinene	1027	C ₁₀ H ₁₆	MH	0.10	-	0.11
11	<i>p</i> -Cymene	1036	C ₁₀ H ₁₄	MH	0.27	-	0.22
12	Limonene	1042	C ₁₀ H ₁₆	MH	3.50	1.75	4.77
13	β -Phellandrene	1044	C ₁₀ H ₁₆	MH	2.77	2.54	3.64
14	(<i>Z</i>)- β -Ocimene	1045	C ₁₀ H ₁₆	MH	-	1.51	-
15	(<i>E</i>)- β -Ocimene	1056	C ₁₀ H ₁₆	MH	0.58	1.58	0.57
16	γ -Terpinene	1065	C ₁₀ H ₁₆	MH	0.18	-	0.20
17	Linalool	1089	C ₁₀ H ₁₈ O	MO	0.17	-	-
18	endo-Borneol	1158	C ₁₀ H ₁₈ O	MO	-	0.36	-
19	Terpinen-4-ol	1165	C ₁₀ H ₁₈ O	MO	0.16	-	0.17
20	α -Terpineol	1179	C ₁₀ H ₁₈ O	MO	0.13	-	0.13
21	α -Cubebene	1340	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	SH	0.25	-	0.38
22	α -Copaene	1373	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	SH	0.52	0.62	0.53
23	β -Bourbonene	1383	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	SH	0.97	0.72	1.34
24	β -Cubebene	1386	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	SH	0.48	-	0.46
25	α -Gurjunene	1408	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	SH	0.23	-	0.36
26	β -Caryophyllene	1424	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	SH	28.85	23.73	24.05
27	β -Copaene	1434	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	SH	0.89	0.72	0.98
28	Aromadendrene	1444	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	SH	-	-	0.27
29	(<i>E</i>)- β -Farnesene	1454	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	SH	2.04	0.82	0.68
30	Humulene	1464	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	SH	15.54	10.71	11.32
31	<i>trans</i> -Cadina-1(6),4-diene	1480	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	SH	0.51	-	0.28
32	γ -Murolene	1484	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	SH	1.01	1.69	1.58
33	Germacrene D	1493	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	SH	17.00	29.37	21.06
34	(<i>Z,E</i>)- α -Farnesene	1497	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	SH	0.66	0.81	0.37
35	γ -Amorphene	1503	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	SH	0.49	-	0.57
36	Bicyclogermacrene	1508	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	SH	3.74	5.66	5.85
37	α -Farnesene	1512	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	SH	0.18	-	0.23
38	δ -Amorphene	1516	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	SH	0.50	-	-
39	γ -Cadinene	1526	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	SH	0.46	0.71	0.63
40	δ -Cadinene	1531	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	SH	1.41	2.24	1.83
41	(<i>E</i>)- α -Bisabolene	1554	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	SH	-	-	2.39
42	Spathulenol	1598	C ₁₅ H ₂₄ O	SO	3.02	1.85	2.52
43	Caryophyllene oxide	1605	C ₁₅ H ₂₄ O	SO	2.98	1.66	1.98
44	Globulol	1608	C ₁₅ H ₂₆ O	SO	0.13	0.41	0.76
45	Salvial-4(14)-en-1-one	1616	C ₁₅ H ₂₄ O	SO	0.23	-	-
46	Humulene epoxide II	1635	C ₁₅ H ₂₄ O	SO	0.83	-	0.49
47	Leden oxide II	1640	C ₁₅ H ₂₄ O	SO	0.32	-	0.23
48	Alloaromadendrene epoxide	1658	C ₁₅ H ₂₄ O	SO	0.47	-	0.42
49	τ -Murolol	1670	C ₁₅ H ₂₆ O	SO	0.51	0.96	0.63
50	Cubenol	1672	C ₁₅ H ₂₆ O	SO	0.46	-	0.29
51	α -Cadinol	1683	C ₁₅ H ₂₆ O	SO	1.13	1.67	1.06
Terpene classes							
Monoterpene hydrocarbons (MH)					9.52	9.87	12.89
Oxygenated monoterpenes (MO)					0.46	0.36	0.30
Sesquiterpene hydrocarbons (SH)					75.73	77.8	75.16
Oxygenated sesquiterpenes (SO)					10.08	6.55	8.38
Others					0.09	-	0.12
Total identified (%)					95.88	94.58	96.85

Figure 2. GC-MS chromatograms of analyzed EOs from different locations. **A.** Panagyurishte region (SV1); **B.** Karlovo region (SV2); **C.** Batak region (SV3), where MCps = mega counts per second, and the numbers refer to the following compounds: 26— β -caryophyllene; 30—humulene; 33—germacrene D; 36—bicyclgermacrene.

The distribution of the terpene classes in the chemical composition of *S. verticillata* EOs is presented as a percentage of the total EO in Fig. 3.

Figure 3. The distribution of the terpene classes as a percentage of the total EO.

The dominant class of terpenes in *S. verticillata* EOs is sesquiterpene hydrocarbons. The percentage of SH in the total oil content of the SV1 and SV3 samples was 75.73% and 75.32%, respectively, while for the SV2 sample, the percentage of SH in the total oil was slightly higher—77.8% (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. The percentage content of each component present in the SH class as a percentage of the total EO.

Monoterpene hydrocarbons are also main components in the phytochemical composition of the EO samples, accounting for 9.52%–12.89% of the total oil content (Fig. 5).

Figure 5. The percentage content of each component present in the MH class as a percentage of the total EO.

This was followed by oxygenated sesquiterpenes (SO), accounting for 6.55%–10.08% (Fig. 6).

Figure 6. The percentage content of each component present in the SO class as a percentage of the total EO.

The content of oxygenated monoterpenes was minimal—0.3%–0.46%—as was that of other compounds, at 0.09%–0.12% (Fig. 7).

Figure 7. The percentage content of each component present in the MO class and the other compounds class as a percentage of the total EO.

Among the represented SH, the highest percentages in all EOs were β -caryophyllene, humulene, germacrene D, and bicyclogermacrene. The highest percentages of β -caryophyllene and humulene were in the SV1 EO—28.85% and 15.54%, respectively; germacrene D (29.37%) was highest in the SV2 sample, with content almost double that in the SV1 sample; and bicyclogermacrene was highest in the SV3 sample—5.85%. Other SH present in all three EOs in amounts above 1% of the total oil content were γ -muurolene (1.01%–1.69%) and δ -cadinene (1.41%–2.24%). β -Bourbonene was above 1% (1.34%) in the SV3 sample, and (*E*)- β -farnesene (2.04%) was above 1% in the SV1 sample.

The examined EOs are characterized by the presence of MH, such as limonene (1.75%–4.47%) and β -phellandrene (2.47%–3.64%). Among the representatives of SO, the highest percentages in all EOs were spathulenol (1.85%–3.02%), caryophyllene oxide (1.66%–2.98%), and α -cadinol (1.06%–1.67%). Endo-borneol (0.36%), a MO, was present only in the SV2 sample. Linalool (MH) was observed only in the SV1 sample, (*Z*)- β -ocimene (MH) in the SV2 sample, and aromadendrene (SH) in the SV3 sample.

Clove oil was considered a natural source of β -caryophyllene and α -humulene (Mendes de Lacerda Leite et al. 2021). However, higher concentrations have been found in EOs from other plant species such as *Zingiber nimmonii* rhizome (β -caryophyllene—42.2% and α -humulene—27.7%) (Sabulal et al. 2006), *Helichrysum* ssp. *barrelieri* var. *scadens* and var. *snatbulaturn* (β -caryophyllene—27.9%–33.6% and α -humulene—13.4%–21.1%) (Roussis et al. 2002), *Callistemon linearis* leaves (β -caryophyllene—29.0% and α -humulene—4.2%) (Brophy et al. 1998), *Humulus lupulus* leaves (β -caryophyllene—12.3%–28.8% and α -humulene—16.4%–23.0%) (Katsiotis et al. 1990), and *Stachys lanata* leaves (β -caryophyllene—12.6% and α -humulene—24.9%) (Mirza and Baher 2003).

Rather than representing discrete and well-defined chemotypes, the analyzed *S. verticillata* populations appear to form a chemotype continuum characterized by varying proportions of key sesquiterpenes. In this context, β -caryophyllene and α -humulene can be considered relatively stable backbone constituents, while germacrene D exhibits pronounced plasticity and acts as the primary differentiating factor among populations. The notably higher abundance of germacrene D in the Karlovo population (SV2), compared to Panagyurishte (SV1) and Batak (SV3), suggests a shift along this continuum toward a germacrene D-enriched profile rather than the presence of a distinct, separate chemotype. This pattern indicates that the phytochemical expression of *S. verticillata* in Bulgaria is likely governed by quantitative modulation of shared biosynthetic pathways, potentially influenced by local environmental conditions, rather than by strict qualitative differences in metabolite presence or absence.

Studies on the chemical composition of *S. verticillata* EO have been conducted in different countries, such as Iran, Turkey, Greece, Serbia, Italy, Romania, and Ukraine. Independent studies in Iran exhibit significant percentages of β -caryophyllene (6.7%–40.98%) and α -humulene (2.9%–15.9%), which vary according to locality and harvest period (Sefidkon and Khajavi 1999; Yousefzadi et al. 2007; Nasermoadeli et al. 2013; Khosravi Dehaghi et al. 2014; Rajabi et al. 2014; Mahdavi et al. 2015; Kameli et al. 2017; Asadollahi et al. 2019). *S. verticillata* EO from Greece and Ukraine did not contain these two components (Pitarokili et al. 2006; Koshovy et al. 2020), and the EO from Turkey contained significantly low percentages of β -caryophyllene (0.7%–3.3%) and α -humulene (0.2%–0.3%) (Aşkun et al. 2010; Hayta et al. 2015; Tabanca et al. 2017; Karakaya et al. 2020). In the present study, the percentage content of β -caryophyllene in lilac sage oil collected from three different locations in Bulgaria was 23.73%–28.85%, and that of humulene was 10.71%–15.54%.

The concentrations of germacrene D and bicyclogermacrene in the composition of *S. verticillata* EOs from Iran differ considerably depending on the harvesting period and locality—0.21%–24.8% and 1.5%–21.07%, respectively (Yousefzadi et al. 2007; Nasermoadeli et al. 2013; Khosravi Dehaghi et al. 2014; Rajabi et al. 2014; Mahdavi et al. 2015; Kameli et al. 2017; Asadollahi et al. 2019; Salehi et al. 2019). Lower concentrations of these two compounds were determined in the EOs from Turkey—1.2%–13.8% and 0.2%–3.3%, respectively (Aşkun et al. 2010; Hayta et al. 2015; Karakaya et al. 2020). In the present study, the percentage content of bicyclogermacrene was 3.74%–5.85%. A more significant difference was observed in the content of germacrene D—17.0%–29.37%.

Coisin et al. reported β -caryophyllene (16.03%) and α -caryophyllene or humulene (14.54%) as the main compounds of the EO from Romania, while the amount of germacrene D was minimal—2.29% (Coisin et al. 2012). *S. verticillata* EO was also investigated by Giuliani et al., and the amount of the main components was found to vary

during different picking periods— β -caryophyllene (7.3%–11.9%), humulene (2.7%–5.9%), germacrene D (39.5%–40.7%), and bicyclogermacrene (11.5%–14.8%) (Giuliani et al. 2018). The content of β -caryophyllene, humulene, germacrene D, and bicyclogermacrene also varied noticeably in *S. verticillata* EOs collected from three different locations in Serbia—10.2%–19.0%, 7.8%–10.2%, 24.6%–48.0%, and 5.3%–16.7%, respectively (Krstic et al. 2006).

In addition to locality and picking period, additional factors that could have an impact on the phytochemical composition of the EO are climatic conditions (Nasermoadeli et al. 2013) and altitude-related variations. External environmental factors could considerably influence the chemical profile and relative abundance of secondary metabolites found. Changes in certain parameters may modify metabolic pathways and biosynthetic activity, resulting in qualitative and quantitative changes in the phytochemical composition. Further differences were observed in the components of wild and cultivated sage EO and in their concentrations (Nasermoadeli et al. 2013). Tomou et al. also demonstrated variability in the composition of EOs isolated from cultivated and wild *S. verticillata*, with the cultivated group predominantly containing oxygenated sesquiterpenes (50.5%), while the wild group was comprised mainly of oxygenated monoterpenes (74.2%) (Tomou et al. 2024). The collection of plant material in a more restricted area is associated with the isolation of EO samples characterized by relative homogeneity (Chizzola 2025). Distinguishing oils from different plant parts is largely possible (Chizzola 2025). In addition to the processed parts of the plant, the drying and storage techniques used are also of great importance, as well as the EO extraction process (Tabanca et al. 2017; Giuliani et al. 2018).

β -Caryophyllene, a bicyclic sesquiterpene, was first isolated from *Eugenia caryophyllata* L. EO in 1834 (Mendes de Lacerda Leite et al. 2021). It is a major component in high concentrations of *S. verticillata* EO, as well as in EOs extracted from *Cannabis sativa*. It also persists in the composition of EOs from black pepper, oregano, mint, thyme, rosemary, basil, cinnamon, and ginger, but in lower concentrations (Hartsel et al. 2016; Francomano et al. 2019). The compound is a selective cannabinoid receptor type 2 (CB2-R) agonist and does not affect type 1 cannabinoid receptors (CB1-R) in the central nervous system or their associated psychoactive effects. It is also known as an atypical cannabinoid. The CB2-R is found mainly in the cells of the immune system and peripheral tissues, with a minimal amount in the central nervous system; its expression increases in diseases such as some tumors, sclerosis, Alzheimer's disease, and Parkinson's disease (Fidy et al. 2016; Hartsel et al. 2016; Francomano et al. 2019). β -Caryophyllene regulates metabolism by affecting the neurotransmitters responsible for energy balance and also affects the immune response (Francomano et al. 2019). It has the potential to be used for the improvement of symptoms in neurodegenerative diseases and for the treatment of neuroinflammation, inflammation, neuropathic

pain, different types of cancer, ischemia, liver and fibrosis ischemia, stroke, depression, anxiety, osteoporosis, atherosclerosis, colitis, obesity, and diabetes (Gertsch et al. 2008; Saturnino et al. 2014; Fidy et al. 2016; Hartsel et al. 2016; Machado et al. 2018; Francomano et al. 2019). In addition, it enhances the process of re-epithelialization and wound healing (Gushiken et al. 2022).

Humulene, or α -caryophyllene, a monocyclic sesquiterpene, is an isomeric form of β -caryophyllene (Hartsel et al. 2016; Mendes de Lacerda Leite et al. 2021). The compound is the characteristic terpene of *Humulus lupulus* and could also be found in sage, cannabis, and ginseng (Hartsel et al. 2016). Several studies have demonstrated the anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, and analgesic effects of α -humulene (Chaves et al. 2008; Rogerio et al. 2009; Jang et al. 2020; Mendes de Lacerda Leite et al. 2021). The compound also stimulates the wound-healing process (Satsu et al. 2004). A potential synergism between humulene and β -caryophyllene with antineoplastic activity has been established (Legault and Pichette 2007; Azizan et al. 2017), as well as antioxidant and gastroprotective activity (Mendes de Lacerda Leite et al. 2021).

Germacrene D is another major component of *S. verticillata* EO and is an intermediate in the biosynthesis of other sesquiterpenes (Steliopoulos et al. 2002). The two enantiomers, (R)-(+)- and (S)-(-)-germacrene D, respectively, are exceptionally present in *Solidago canadensis*, and their ratio varies (Steliopoulos et al. 2002). Germacrenes are known for their anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, anticancer, antifungal, and insecticidal activity (Adio 2009; Dhyani et al. 2022).

Bicyclogermacrene is a sesquiterpene derived from germacrene with described fungistatic, cytotoxic, and acetylcholinesterase-inhibitory activity (Durán-Peña et al. 2015). Bicyclogermacrene also has antibacterial activity, especially against gram-positive bacteria (*Staphylococcus aureus* and *Bacillus cereus*) (Santos et al. 2013).

The data obtained from the comparative analysis of the phytochemical composition of the investigated wild-growing *S. verticillata* EOs from three different locations in Bulgaria indicated slight variability in the percentage content of the main compounds— β -caryophyllene, humulene, and bicyclogermacrene—except for germacrene D, where the differences are more prominent. The components in lower concentrations in the EOs also vary in percentage content or are completely absent. Based on these results, the plant growing location may influence the chemical composition of the EOs.

S. verticillata could become a potential alternative source of these important bioactive compounds with various proven biological activities—antioxidant, antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, gastroprotective, neuroprotective, and hypoglycemic activity (Coisin et al. 2012; Asadollahi et al. 2019; Mendes de Lacerda Leite et al. 2021; Mervić et al. 2022). Moreover, the EOs may support possible applications as wound-healing agents, aiding the re-epithelialization process (Salas-Oropeza et al. 2021; Gushiken et al. 2022).

Conclusion

This study provides a detailed comparative characterization of EOs obtained from wild populations of *Salvia verticillata* L. collected from three geographically distinct regions of Bulgaria. GC–MS analyses demonstrated that the EOs are dominated by sesquiterpene hydrocarbons, with β -caryophyllene, α -humulene, germacrene D, and bicyclogermacrene identified as the principal constituents. While β -caryophyllene and α -humulene exhibited relatively stable concentrations across the studied populations, germacrene D showed substantial variability, indicating a pronounced chemogeographical effect. Variations in minor constituents further support the influence of environmental and ecological factors on the secondary metabolite profile of the species. These findings contribute to the existing knowledge of intraspecific chemical variability in *S. verticillata* and position Bulgarian

populations within the broader European chemotypic framework. The high abundance of biologically active sesquiterpenes reinforces the potential of this species as a natural source of compounds with pharmacological relevance. Future investigations integrating ecological parameters, seasonal dynamics, and bioactivity-guided assays are necessary to clarify the drivers of variability and to support standardization strategies for prospective pharmaceutical or nutraceutical applications.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

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Author contributions

Conceptualization, S.I. and Z.D.; methodology, S.I. and Z.D.; software, S.I., Z.D., and H.M.; formal analysis, S.I., Z.D., and H.M.; investigation, S.I., Z.D., and H.M.; resources, Z.D., and V.N.; data curation, Z.D.; writing—original draft preparation, Z.D. and V.N.; writing—review and editing, S.I.; visualization, S.I., K.I., E.A., R.E., R.A., and D.G.-K.; supervision, S.I. and K.I. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.